

AGROSYM

BOOK OF PROCEEDINGS

*XV International Scientific Agriculture Symposium
"Agrosym 2024"
Jahorina, October 10-13, 2024*

AgroSym
2024

AGRO 2024
sym

BOOK OF PROCEEDINGS

**XV International Scientific Agriculture Symposium
“AGROSYM 2024”**

Jahorina, October 10 - 13, 2024

Impressum

XV International Scientific Agriculture Symposium „AGROSYM 2024“

Book of Proceedings Published by

University of East Sarajevo, Faculty of Agriculture, Republic of Srpska, Bosnia
University of Belgrade, Faculty of Agriculture, Serbia
Mediterranean Agronomic Institute of Bari (CIHEAM - IAMB) Italy
International Society of Environment and Rural Development, Japan
Balkan Environmental Association (B.EN.A), Greece
CDR, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences (BOKU), Austria
Perm State Agro-Technological University, Russia
Voronezh State Agricultural University named after Peter The Great, Russia
Tokyo University of Agriculture, Japan
Jiangsu University, People's Republic of China
Shinshu University, Japan
Faculty of Agriculture, University of Western Macedonia, Greece
Arid Agricultural University, Rawalpindi, Pakistan
Chapingo Autonomous University, Mexico
Selçuk University, Turkey
University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of Bucharest, Romania
Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra, Slovakia
National University of Life and Environmental Sciences of Ukraine, Kyiv, Ukraine
Saint Petersburg State Forest Technical University, Russia
University of Valencia, Spain
Faculty of Agriculture, University of Zagreb, Croatia
Voronezh State University of Forestry and Technologies, Russia
Tarbiat Modares University, Islamic Republic of Iran
Northwest Normal University, People's Republic of China
Valahia University of Targoviste, Romania
Faculty of Agriculture, University of Akdeniz - Antalya, Turkey
Cangzhou Normal University, People's Republic of China
Ukrainian Institute for Plant Variety Examination, Kyiv, Ukraine
Institute of Animal Science - Kostinbrod, Bulgaria
National Scientific Center "Institute of Agriculture of NAAS", Kyiv, Ukraine
Department of Agricultural, Food and Environmental Sciences, University of Perugia, Italy
Watershed Management Society of Iran
Faculty of Agriculture, Cairo University, Egypt
Higher Institute of Agronomy, Chott Mariem-Sousse, Tunisia
Faculty of Economics Brcko, University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Biotechnical Faculty, Montenegro
Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, Serbia
Institute of Lowland Forestry and Environment, Serbia
Institute for Applied Science in Agriculture, Serbia
Agricultural Institute of Republic of Srpska - Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Maize Research Institute “Zemun Polje”, Serbia
Faculty of Agriculture, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Institute for Animal Science, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje, North Macedonia
Serbian Academy of Engineering Sciences, Serbia
Balkan Scientific Association of Agricultural Economics, Serbia
Institute of Agricultural Economics, Serbia

Editor in Chief

Dusan Kovacevic

Technical editors

Sinisa Berjan
Milan Jugovic
Rosanna Quagliariello

Website:

<http://agrosym.ues.rs.ba>

CIP - Каталогизација у публикацији
Народна и универзитетска библиотека
Републике Српске, Бања Лука

631(082)(0.034.2)

INTERNATIONAL Scientific Agriculture Symposium "AGROSYM"
(15 ; 2024 ; Jahorina)

Book of Proceedings [Електронски извор] / XV International
Scientific Agriculture Symposium "AGROSYM 2024", Jahorina,
October 10 - 13, 2024 ; [editor in chief Dusan Kovacevic]. - Onlajn
izd. - El. zbornik. - East Sarajevo : Faculty of Agriculture, 2024

Системски захтјеви: Нису наведени. - Наћин pristupa (URL):
https://agrosym.ues.rs.ba/article/showpdf/BOOK_OF_PROCEEDINGS_2024_FINAL.pdf. - Ел. публикација у ПДФ формату опсега
1552 стр. - Насл. са насловног екрана. - Опис извора дана
2.12.2024. - Библиографија уз сваки рад. - Регистар.

ISBN 978-99976-816-8-3

COBISS.RS-ID 141807105

**XV International Scientific Agricultural Symposium “Agrosym 2024”
Jahorina, October 10-13, 2024, Bosnia and Herzegovina**

HONORARY COMMITTEE

- Mr. Savo Minic**, Minister of Agriculture, Water Management and Forestry of Republic of Srpska, Bosnia and Herzegovina
- Dr. Zeljko Budimir**, Minister of Scientific-Technological Development, Higher Education and Information Society of Republic of Srpska, Bosnia and Herzegovina
- Prof. dr Mario T. Tabucanon**, President of the International Society of Environment and Rural Development, Japan
- Prof. dr Milan Kulic**, Rector of the University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
- Prof. dr Dusan Zivkovic**, Dean of the Faculty of Agriculture, University of Belgrade, Serbia
- Dr. Maurizio Raeli**, Director of the Mediterranean Agronomic Institute of Bari, Italy
- Prof. Dr. Hüseyin YILMAZ**, Rector of the Selcuk University, Turkey
- Prof. dr Aleksey Andreev**, Rector of the Perm State Agro-Technological University, Russia
- Prof. dr Alexey Yu. Popov**, Rector of the Voronezh State Agricultural University named after Peter The Great, Russia
- Prof. dr Zhang Jijian**, President of Jiangsu University, People’s Republic of China
- Prof. dr Barbara Hinterstoisser**, Vice-Rector of the University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences (BOKU), Austria
- Prof. dr Sorin Mihai Cimpeanu**, Rector of the University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of Bucharest, Romania
- Prof. Shinichi Yonekura**, Vice-President of the Shinshu University, Japan
- Doc. Ing. Klaudia Halászová**, Rector of the Slovak University of Agriculture in Nitra, Slovakia
- Prof. dr Calin D. Oros**, Rector of the Valahia University of Targoviste, Romania
- Prof. Dr Katerina Melfou**, Dean of the Faculty of Agriculture, University of Western Macedonia, Greece
- Prof. dr Amr Ahmed Mostafa**, Dean of the Faculty of Agriculture, Cairo University, Egypt
- Prof. dr José Sergio Barrales Domínguez**, Rector of the Chapingo Autonomous University, Mexico
- Prof. dr Davut Karayel**, Dean of Faculty of Agriculture, University of Akdeniz - Antalya, Turkey
- Prof. Dr Eguchi Fumio**, Rector of the Tokyo University of Agriculture, Japan
- Prof. dr Muhammad Naeem**, Vice-Chancellor of Arid Agricultural University, Rawalpindi, Pakistan
- Prof. dr Zhang Zhanping**, President of Cangzhou Normal University, People's Republic of China
- Prof. dr Wang Zhanren**, President of Northwest Normal University, People's Republic of China
- Dr Chokri Thabet**, the General Director of the High Agronomic Institute of Chott Mariem, Sousse, Tunisia
- Prof. dr Maya Ignatova**, Director of the Institute of Animal Science- Kostinbrod, Bulgaria
- Prof. dr Seyed Hamidreza Sadeghi**, Professor at Tarbiat Modares University and the President of the Watershed Management Society of Iran, Iran
- Prof. dr Francesco Tei**, Director of the Department of Agricultural, Food and Environmental Sciences, University of Perugia, Italy
- Prof. dr Viktor Kaminskyi**, Director of National Scientific Center „Institute of Agriculture of NAAS“, Kyiv, Ukraine
- Dr. Igor Hrovatič**, President of South Eastern Advisory Service Network, Croatia
- Prof. dr Mirza Dautbasic**, Dean of the Faculty of Forestry, University of Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
- Prof. dr Bozidarka Markovic**, Dean of the Biotechnical Faculty, University of Podgorica, Montenegro
- Prof. dr Rade Jovanovic**, Director of the Institute for Science Application in Agriculture, Serbia
- Prof. dr Lazar Radovanovic**, Dean of the Faculty of Economics Brcko, University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
- Prof. dr Vojislav Trkulja**, Director of Agricultural Institute of Republic of Srpska - Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina
- Dr. Miodrag Tolimir**, Director of the Maize Research Institute “Zemun Polje”, Serbia
- Prof. Dr. Jegor Miladinović**, Director of the Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, Serbia
- Prof. dr Nedeljko Tica**, Dean of the Faculty of Agriculture, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
- Prof. dr Rodne Nastova**, Director of the Institute for Animal Science, Skoplje, Macedonia
- Prof. dr Sasa Orlovic**, Director of the Institute of Lowland Forestry and Environment, Serbia
- Prof. dr Jonel Subic**, Director of the Institute of Agricultural Economics, Serbia
- Prof. dr Branko Kovacevic**, President of the Academy of Engineering Sciences of Serbia, Serbia
- Prof. dr Radovan Pejanovic**, President of Balkan Scientific Association of Agricultural Economics, Serbia

SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE

Chairman: Academician Prof. dr Dusan Kovacevic, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Prof. dr Machito Mihara, Tokyo University of Agriculture, Japan
Prof. dr John Brayden, Norwegian Agricultural Economics Research Institute (NILF), Norway
Prof. dr Steve Quarie, Visiting Professor, School of Biology, Newcastle University, United Kingdom
Prof. dr Andreas Melcher, CDR, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences (BOKU), Vienna, Austria
Prof. dr Dieter Trautz, University of Applied Science, Germany
Prof. dr Mustafa Harmankaya, Dean of Faculty of Agriculture, University of Selçuk- Konya, Turkey
Prof. dr Sergei Eliseev, Vice-Rector for Research and Innovations, Perm State Agro-Technological University, Russia
Prof. dr Dani Shtienberg, full professor, Department of Plant pathology and Weed Research, ARO, the Volcani Center, Bet Dagan, Israel
Prof. dr William Meyers, Howard Cowden Professor of Agricultural and Applied Economics, University of Missouri, USA
Prof. dr Markus Schermer, Department of Sociology, University of Innsbruck, Austria
Prof. dr Thomas G. Johnson, University of Missouri – Columbia, USA
Prof. dr Fokion Papathanasiou, School of Agricultural Sciences, University of Western Macedonia, Greece
Prof. dr Sabahudin Bajramovic, Faculty of Agriculture and Food Sciences, University of Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Prof. dr Hiromu Okazawa, Faculty of Regional Environment Science, Tokyo University of Agriculture, Japan
Prof. dr Tatiana Sivkova, Faculty for Veterinarian Medicine and Zootechny, Perm State Agro-Technological University, Russia
Prof. dr Aleksej Lukin, Voronezh State Agricultural University named after Peter The Great, Russia
Prof. dr Matteo Vittuari, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Bologna, Italy
Prof. Katsuharu Saito, Faculty of Agriculture, Shinshu University, Japan
Prof. dr Seyed Mohsen Hosseini, Faculty of Natural Resources, Tarbiat Modares University, Iran
Prof. dr Ardian Maci, Faculty of Agriculture and Environment, Agricultural University of Tirana, Albania
Prof. dr Regucivilla A. Pobar, Bohol Island State University, Philippines
Prof. dr Azeem Khalid, Arid Agriculture University, Rawalpindi, Pakistan
Prof. dr Aayesha Riaz, Arid Agriculture University, Rawalpindi, Pakistan
Prof. dr Munir Ahmad, Arid Agriculture University, Rawalpindi, Pakistan
Prof. dr Sudheer Kundukulangara Pulissery, Kerala Agricultural University, India
Prof. dr EPN Udayakumara, Faculty of Applied Sciences, Sabaragamuwa University, Sri Lanka
Prof. dr Vladimir Smutný, full professor, Mendel University, Faculty of agronomy, Czech Republic
Prof. dr Franc Bavec, full professor, Faculty of Agriculture and Life Sciences, Maribor, Slovenia
Prof. dr Jan Moudrý, full professor, Faculty of Agriculture, South Bohemia University, Czech Republic
Prof. dr Stefan Tyr, full professor, Faculty of Agro-biology and Food Resources, Slovakia
Prof. dr Natalija Bogdanov, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Prof. dr Richard Barichello, Faculty of Land and Food Systems, University of British Columbia, Canada
Prof. dr Francesco Porcelli, University of Bari Aldo Moro, Italy
Prof. dr Vasilije Isajev, Faculty of Forestry, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Prof. dr Elazar Fallik, Agricultural Research Organization (ARO), Volcani, Israel
Prof. dr Junaid Alam Memon, Pakistan Institute of Development Economics, Pakistan
Prof. dr. Jorge Batlle-Sales, Department of Biology, University of Valencia, Spain
Prof. dr Pandi Zdruli, Land and Water Resources Department; IAMB, Italy
Prof. dr Mladen Todorovic, Land and Water Resources Department; IAMB, Italy
Dr. Hamid El Bilali, Mediterranean Agronomic Institute of Bari, Italy
Prof. dr Maksym Melnychuk, National Academy of Agricultural Science of Ukraine, Ukraine
Prof. dr Borys Sorochynskiy, Ukrainian Institute for Plant Variety Examination, Kyiv, Ukraine
Dr. Lorenz Probst, CDR, University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences (BOKU), Vienna, Austria
Prof. Dragana Sunjka, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Prof. dr Miodrag Dimitrijevic, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Prof. dr Mohsen Boubaker, High Institute of Agronomy of Chott Meriem, Sousse, Tunisia
Dr. Nouredin Driouech, Coordinator of MAIB Alumni Network (FTN), Mediterranean Agronomic Institute of Bari, Italy
Prof. dr Ion Viorel, University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of Bucharest, Romania
Prof. dr. Chuleemas Boonthai Iwai, Faculty of Agriculture, Khon Kaen University, Thailand
Prof. dr Wathuge T.P.S.K. Senarath, Department of Botany, University of Sri Jayewardenepura, Colombo, Sri Lanka

Dr. Hamada Abdelrahman, Soil Science Dept., Faculty of Agriculture, Cairo University, Egypt
Prof. dr Maya Ignatova, Director of the Institute of Animal Science- Kostinbrod, Bulgaria
Prof. dr Ioannis N. Xynias, School of Agricultural Technology & Food Technology and Nutrition, Western Macedonia University of Applied Sciences, Greece
PhD ing. Artur Rutkiewicz, Department of Forest Protection, Institute of Forest Sciences, Warsaw University of Life Sciences - SGGW, Poland
Prof. dr Mohammad Sadegh Allahyari, Islamic Azad University, Rasht Branch, Iran
Dr. Lalita Siri wattananon, Faculty of Agricultural Technology, Rajamangala University of Technology Thanyaburi (RMUTT), Thailand
Prof. dr Konstantin Korlyakov, Perm Agricultural Research Institute, Russia
Dr. Mohammad Farooque Hassan, Shaheed Benazir Bhutto University of Veterinary & Animal Sciences Sakrand, Sindh, Pakistan
Dr. Larysa Prysiazhniuk, Ukrainian Institute for Plant Variety Examination, Kyiv, Ukraine
Prof. dr Oksana Kliachenko, National University of Life and Environmental Science of Ukraine, Ukraine
Prof. dr Ivan Simunic, Department of amelioration, Faculty of agriculture, University of Zagreb, Croatia
Dr. Abid Hussain, International Centre for Integrated Mountain Development (ICIMOD), Nepal
Dr. Amrita Ghatak, Gujarat Institute of Development Research (GIDR), India
Prof. dr Naser Sabaghnia, University of Maragheh, Iran
Dr. Karol Wajszczuk, Poznan University of Life Sciences, Poland
Prof. dr Penka Moneva, Institute of Animal Science - Kostinbrod, Bulgaria
Prof. dr Mostafa K. Nassar, Animal husbandry Dept., Faculty of Agriculture, Cairo University, Egypt
Prof. dr Márta Birkás, full professor, St. Istvan University, Godollo - Hungary
Prof. dr Andrzej Kowalski, Director of the Institute for Agricultural and Food Economy, Warszawa-Poland
Prof. dr Yalcin Kaya, The Director of the Plant Breeding Research Center, University of Trakya, Turkey
Prof. dr Sanja Radonjic, Biotechnical Faculty, University of Montenegro, Montenegro
Prof. dr Ionela Dobrin, Department for Plant Protection, University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of Bucharest, Romania
Prof. dr Inocencio Buot Jr., Institute of Biological Sciences, College of Arts and Sciences, University of the Philippines Los Banos, Philippines
Prof. dr Monica Paula Marin, Department for Animal Husbandry, University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of Bucharest, Romania
Prof. dr Nedeljka Nikolova, Institute for Animal Science, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje, Republic of Macedonia
Prof. dr Mohammad Al-Mamun, Department of Animal Nutrition, Bangladesh Agricultural University, Bangladesh
Prof. dr Anucha Wittayakorn-Puripunpinyoo, School of Agriculture and Co-operatives, Sukhothai Thammathirat Open University, Nonthaburi, Thailand
Dr. Redouane Choukr-Allah, International Center for Biosaline Agriculture (ICBA), United Arab Emirates
Prof. dr Ignacio J. Díaz-Maroto, High School Polytechnic, University of Santiago de Compostela, Spain
Prof. dr Nidal Shaban, University of Forestry Sofia, Bulgaria
Prof. dr Mehdi Shafaghati, Faculty of Geography, Tarbiat Moalem (kharazmi) University, Iran
Prof. dr Youssif Sassine, Lebanese University Beirut, Lebanon
Prof. dr Cafer Topaloglu, Faculty of Tourism, Mugla Sitki Kocman University, Turkey
Prof. dr Seyed Hamidreza Sadeghi, Faculty of Natural Resources, Tarbiat Modares University, Iran
Prof. Zain Ul Abdin, Department of Entomology, University of Agriculture, Faisalabad, Pakistan
Prof. dr Mohsen Mohseni Saravi, University of Teheran and Member of WMSI Management Board, Iran
Prof. dr Branislav Draskovic, Faculty of Agriculture, University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Prof. dr Mahmood Arabkhedri, Soil Conservation and Watershed Management Research Institute and Member of WMSI Management Board, Iran
Prof. dr Ataollah Kaviani, Sari Agricultural Science and Natural Resources University and Member of WMSI Management Board, Iran
Prof. dr Tugay Ayasan, Department of Organic Farming Business Management, Osmaniye, Applied Science School of Kadirli, Osmaniye Korkut Ata University, Turkey
Prof. dr Sakine Özpınar, Department of Farm Machinery and Technologies Engineering, Faculty of Agriculture, Çanakkale Onsekiz Mart University, Çanakkale, Turkey
Prof. dr Sherein Saeide Abdelgayed, Faculty of Veterinary Medicine, Cairo University, Cairo, Egypt
Prof. dr Zohreh Mashak, Islamic Azad University, Karaj Branch, Iran
Dr. Khalid Azim, National Institute of Agriculture Research, Morocco
Dr. Mario Licata, Department of Agricultural, Food and Forest Sciences, University of Palermo, Italy
Prof. dr Srdjan Lalic, University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Prof. Fatiha Addyoubah, Moulay Ismail University, Morocco
Prof. dr Muhammad Ovais Omer, Faculty of Bio-Sciences, University of Veterinary & Animal Sciences, Lahore, Pakistan
Dr. Edouard Musabanganji, School of Economics/CBE, University of Rwanda, Rwanda
Prof. dr Kubilay Baştaş, Department of Plant Protection, Faculty of Agriculture, Selçuk University, Turkey
Dr. Branka Kresovic, Director of the Maize Research Institute “Zemun Polje”, Serbia
Dr. Nenad Delic, Maize Research Institute “Zemun Polje”, Serbia
Dr. Milan Stevanovic, Maize Research Institute “Zemun Polje”, Serbia
Prof. Violeta Babic, Faculty of Forestry, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Dr. Svetlana Balesevic-Tubic, Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops Novi Sad, Serbia
Dr. Ana Marjanovic Jeromela, Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops Novi Sad, Serbia
Prof. dr Tatjana Krajsnik, Faculty of Agriculture, University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Prof. dr Aleksandra Govedarica-Lucic, Faculty of Agriculture, University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Prof. dr Desimir Knezevic, University of Pristina, Faculty of Agriculture, Kosovska Mitrovica - Lesak, Kosovo i Metohija, Serbia
Dr. Snezana Mladenovic-Drinic, Maize Research Institute “Zemun Polje”, Serbia
Prof. dr Nebojsa Momirovic, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Prof. dr Osman Mujezinovic, Faculty of Forestry, University of Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Prof. dr Dalibor Ballian, Faculty of Forestry, University of Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Prof. dr Zoran Jovovic, Biotechnical Faculty, University of Montenegro, Montenegro
Prof. dr Danijel Jug, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Osijek, Croatia
Prof. dr Milan Markovic, Biotechnical Faculty, University of Montenegro, Montenegro
Prof. dr Zeljko Dolijanovic, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Prof. Mirjana Jovovic, Faculty of Agriculture, University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Prof. dr Dejana Stanic, Faculty of Agriculture, University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Prof. Goran Marinkovic, Faculty of Technical Sciences, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Dr Dejan Stojanovic, Institute of Lowland Forestry and Environment, Serbia
Dr Dobrivoj Postic, Institute for plant protection and environment, Belgrade, Serbia
Dr Srdjan Stojnic, Institute of Lowland Forestry and Environment, Serbia
Dunja Demirović Bajrami, Research Associate, Geographical Institute “Jovan Cvijić,” Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts, Belgrade, Serbia

ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITTEE

Chairperson: Prof. dr Vesna Milic, Dean of the Faculty of Agriculture, University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Dr Marko Gutalj, Vice rector of the University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Dr Jelena Kronic, Vice rector of the University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Dr. Maroun El Moujabber, Mediterranean Agronomic Institute of Bari, Italy
Mrs. Rosanna Quagliariello, Mediterranean Agronomic Institute of Bari, Italy
Dr. Nouredin Driouech, Coordinator of MAIB Alumni Network (FTN), Mediterranean Agronomic Institute of Bari, Italy
Dr Milic Curovic, The journal “Agriculture and Forestry”, Biotechnical Faculty Podgorica, University of Montenegro, Montenegro
Dr. Tatiana Lysak, International Relations Office, Voronezh State Agricultural University named after Peter The Great, Russia
Dr. Oksana Fotina, International Relations Center, Perm State Agro-Technological University, Russia
Prof. dr Fokion Papathanasiou, School of Agricultural Sciences, University of Western Macedonia, Greece
Dr Ana Marjanović Jeromela, Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, Serbia
Prof. dr Engr. Teodora Popova, Institute of Animal Science - Kostinbrod, Bulgaria
Prof. dr Mehmet Musa Ozcan, Faculty of Agriculture, Selçuk University, Turkey
Prof. dr Arfan Yousaf, Arid Agricultural University, Rawalpindi, Pakistan
Dr. Abdulvahed Khaledi Darvishan, Faculty of Natural Resources, Tarbiat Modares University, Iran
Prof. dr Nikola Pacinovski, Institute for Animal Science, Ss. Cyril and Methodius University in Skopje, N. Macedonia
MSc. Erasmo Velázquez Cigarroa, Department of Rural Sociology, Chapingo Autonomous University, Mexico
Dr. Ecaterina Stefan, University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine of Bucharest, Romania
Dr. Jeeranuch Sakkhamduang, The International Society of Environmental and Rural Development, Japan

Dr. Raoudha Khanfir Ben Jenana, High Institute of Agronomy of Chott Meriem, Sousse, Tunisia
Dr. Hamada Abdelrahman, Soil Science Dept., Faculty of Agriculture, Cairo University, Egypt
Prof. Dragana Sunjka, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
MSc. Aleksandra Susnjar, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
MSc. Dragana Boskovic, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Dr. Antonije Zunic, Faculty of Agriculture, University of Novi Sad, Serbia
Dr. Vedran Tomic, Institute for Science Application in Agriculture, Serbia
MSc. Vojin Cvijanovic, Institute for Science Application in Agriculture, Serbia
MSc. Mladen Petrovic, Institute of Agricultural Economics, Serbia
Dr. Milan Stevanovic, Maize Research Institute "Zemun Polje", Serbia
Dr. Andrej Pilipovic, Institute of Lowland Forestry and Environment, Serbia
Dr. Sc. Morteza Behzadfar, Tarbiat Modares University, Tehran, Iran
Dr. Larysa Prysiashniuk, Ukrainian Institute for Plant Variety Examination, Kyiv, Ukraine
Doc. dr Sead Ivojevic, Faculty of Forestry, University of Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Dr. Nenad Markovic, Enterprise E. N. (EEN) Coordinator, University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Domagoj Group, SEASN - South Eastern Advisory Service Network, Croatia
Dr. Milan Ninkovic, Scientific Institute of Veterinary Medicine of Serbia
Prof. dr Zeljko Lakic, Agricultural Institute of Republic of Srpska - Banja Luka, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Dr. Milan Jugovic, Faculty of Agriculture, University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Prof. dr Sinisa Berjan, Faculty of Agriculture, University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Prof. dr Dejana Stanic, Faculty of Agriculture, University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
MSc. Milena Stankovic, Faculty of Agriculture, University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Dr. Stefan Stjepanovic, Faculty of Agriculture, University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
MSc. Stefan Bojic, Faculty of Agriculture, University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Dr. Tanja Jakisic, Faculty of Agriculture, University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Dr. Boban Miletic, Faculty of Agriculture, University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Doc. dr Nedeljka Elez, Faculty of Agriculture, University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
MSc. Selena Cevriz, Faculty of Agriculture, University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina
Dr. Branka Govedarica, Faculty of Agriculture, University of East Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina

CONTENT

PLANT PRODUCTION	31
CROP PRODUCTION: CURRENT STATE AND CHALLENGES, ADVANCES AND PROSPECTS TO BALANCE ENVIRONMENTAL, SOCIAL AND ECONOMIC IMPERATIVES	
Steve QUARRIE	32
GENETIC IMPROVEMENT OF DATE PALMS - PROTOPLASTS CULTURE OF TEGGAZA, DEGLET NOUR AND TAQUERBUCHT CULTIVARS	
Djamila YATTA-EL DJOUZI, Said. BOUDEFFEUR, Rosa. SLAMANI, Radia. AYADI, Sana. EZZOUAOUI, Lydia BOUAMRA, Mohamed KHARSSI	43
AGRICULTURAL ADAPTATION TO CLIMATE CHANGE IN ALGERIA	
Wassila HANAFAI, Nouara BOULFOUL	50
FACILITATING HYSSOP INTRODUCTION TO ARMENIA: ASSESSING GLOBAL GENE BANK RESOURCES AND CULTIVATION POTENTIAL	
Alvina AVAGYAN, Laura TADEVOSYAN, Raya BALAYAN, Vladimíra HORČINOVÁ SEDLÁČKOVÁ, Marina HOVHANNISYAN, Margarita HARUTYUNYAN	54
A STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF BIOSTIMULANT ON THE YIELD AND QUALITY OF CUCUMBER (CUCUMIS SATIVUS)	
Aleksandra GOVEDARICA-LUČIĆ, Tanja PEROVIĆ, Alma MEMIĆ, Lutvija KARIĆ, Čerima ZAHIROVIĆ SINANOVIĆ Milica STOJANOVIĆ	60
INTERDEPENDENCE OF PRODUCTIVE CHARACTERISTICS AND FORAGE QUALITY OF RED CLOVER	
Borislav PETKOVIĆ, Ilija KOMLJENOVIĆ, Vojo RADIĆ, Mihajlo MARKOVIĆ, Zoran MALIČEVIĆ	65
ECOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MACROPHYTES OF THE PROTECTED HABITAT "GROMIŽELJ" (BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA)	
Milica LJUBOJEVIĆ, Natasa MARIC, Sladjana PETRONIC	71
ORGANIC PLANT BIOSTIMULANTS AND TOMATO FRUIT QUALITY	
Mirjana JOVOVIĆ, Verica MILOVIĆ, Zoranka MALEŠEVIĆ, Marko PETKOVIĆ	77
FLOWERING AND FRUIT SET OF CULTIVARS OF SWEET CHERRY IN AGRO-ECOLOGICAL CONDITIONS OF SARAJEVO	
Mirjana RADOVIĆ, Mihajlo LIZDEK, Mirko KULINA, Dejan ZEJAK, Dragan TOMOVIĆ, Slavisa MILOVANOVIĆ	84
PROSPECTS OF CORN CULTIVATION AND PRODUCTION IN THE SEMBERIJA REGION IN BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA	
Igor ĐURĐIĆ, Nedeljka ELEZ, Angelina PETKOVIĆ, Slađana JANKOVIĆ	90
YIELD AND CHARACTERISTICS OF BUNCHES OF RED WINE VARIETIES GROWN IN THE AREA OF TREBINJE (BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA)	
Tijana BANJANIN, Snežana BRKLJAČ, Zorica RANKOVIĆ VASIĆ	96

MARKER ASSISTED SELECTION FOR β -CAROTENE RICH MAIZE: VALIDATION OF MULTIPLEX-PCR ASSAY FOR *crtRB1* AND *lcyE* FAVOURABLE ALLELES

Marija KOSTADINOVIĆ, Danijela RISTIĆ, Milica LUČEV, Dragana IGNJATOVIĆ-MIČIĆ, Jelena VANČETOVIĆ..... 334

INFLUENCE OF THE CULTIVAR, FERTILISER, AND IRRIGATION ON ICEBERG LETTUCE MORPHOLOGY - SINGLE FACTOR VS INTERACTION EFFECTS

Milica STOJANOVIĆ, Zoran DINIĆ, Dragica MILOSAVLJEVIĆ, Aleksandra GOVEDARICA-LUČIĆ, Đorđe MORAVČEVIĆ, Jelena DRAGIŠIĆ MAKSIMOVIĆ, Vuk MAKSIMOVIĆ 339

NOVEL BATAVIA LETTUCE CULTIVARS-CHOOSING THE OPTIMAL CULTIVAR FOR FRESH AND PROCESSED PRODUCTS USING WASPAS METHOD

Milica STOJANOVIĆ, Dragica MILOSAVLJEVIĆ, Jelena DRAGIŠIĆ MAKSIMOVIĆ, Vuk MAKSIMOVIĆ, Aleksandra GOVEDARICA-LUČIĆ, Radomir BODIROGA 346

YIELD RESPONSE OF MAIZE TO IRRIGATION AND PLANTING DENSITY IN THE VOJVODINA ENVIRONMENT IN SERBIA

Miodrag TOLIMIR, Branka KRESOVIĆ, Zorica SREDOJEVIĆ, Katarina GAJIĆ, Milan BRANKOV, Marijana DUGALIĆ, Boško GAJIĆ 353

STRESS RESISTANCE INDICATORS AS THE TOOL FOR SELECTING DROUGHT-TOLERANT WHEAT GENOTYPES

Mirela MATKOVIĆ STOJŠIN, Veselinka ZEČEVIĆ, Dušan UROŠEVIĆ, Dragan BOŽOVIĆ, Jasmina BAČIĆ, Kamenko BRATKOVIĆ, Desimir KNEŽEVIĆ..... 361

SOCIAL NETWORKING IN STRESS-EXPOSED PLANTS

Mirjana VUKOSAVLJEV, Brankica KARTALOVIĆ, Nevena STEVANOVIĆ, Maša BUĐEN, Nikola STANKOVIĆ, Boris BRKIĆ, Nataša LJUBIČIĆ 367

THE NORMALIZED DIFFERENCE RED EDGE INDEX (NDRE) IN GRAIN YIELD AND BIOMASS ESTIMATION IN MAIZE (*Zea mays* L.)

Nataša LJUBIČIĆ, Vera POPOVIĆ, Marko KOSTIĆ, Mirjana VUKOSAVLJEV, Maša BUĐEN, Nikola STANKOVIĆ, Nevena STEVANOVIĆ..... 373

MONITORING STRESS IN ARUGULA (*Eruca sativa*) USING A PORTABLE MULTISPECTRAL DEVICE

Nevena STEVANOVIĆ, Nataša LJUBIČIĆ, Nikola STANKOVIĆ, Maša BUĐEN, Brankica KARTALOVIĆ, Mirjana VUKOSAVLJEV 379

EFFECTS OF NITROGEN FERTILIZATION ON THE YIELD OF TRADITIONAL VARIETIES AND LANDRACES OF WINTER WHEAT

Sanja MIKIĆ, Milan MIROSAVLJEVIĆ, Ljiljana BRBAKLIĆ, Vladimir AĆIN, Jelena VISKOVIĆ, Goran JAĆIMOVIĆ 384

RESULTS OF TESTING THE WORKING QUALITY OF DIFFERENT TECHNOLOGICAL-TECHNICAL SYSTEMS FOR PRECISION SOWING OF MAIZE

Saša BARAĆ, Milan BIBERDŽIĆ, Aleksandar ĐIKIĆ, Aleksandar VUKOVIĆ, Dragana LALEVIĆ 392

PLANT PRODUCTION

EFFECTS OF NITROGEN FERTILIZATION ON THE YIELD OF TRADITIONAL VARIETIES AND LANDRACES OF WINTER WHEAT

Sanja MIKIĆ^{1*}, Milan MIROSAVLJEVIĆ¹, Ljiljana BRBAKLIĆ¹, Vladimir AĆIN¹, Jelena VISKOVIĆ², Goran JAĆIMOVIĆ²

¹Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops, National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, Maksima Gorkog 30, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

²Faculty of Agriculture, University of Novi Sad, Dositej Obradović Square 8, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

*Corresponding author: sanja.mikic@ifvcns.ns.ac.rs

Abstract

The intensification of agriculture and modern breeding activities have reduced biological diversity and led to the nearly-complete elimination of old varieties and local landraces from farms. The aim of this study was to examine the effect of nitrogen application on the main yield components and grain yield of five old, traditional wheat landraces and varieties. The experiment was conducted as a two-factorial trial with a randomized treatment design. The following factors and treatments were examined: five winter wheat varieties - Stara Banatka, Bezostaya 1, Bankut 1205, Crnozrna, and Brkulja 4; and nitrogen fertilization with two treatments: a) control (N₀) and b) nitrogen fertilization in top-dressing based on N-min analysis (N₁₀₉). For all analyzed traits, the analysis of variance showed that the varieties had the largest contribution to their variability, suggesting significant genetic differences among the varieties, which can be attributed to their different origins and varietal specificity. The Crnozrna variety produced the highest grain mass per spike while the variety Bezostaya 1 had the highest 1000-grain weight. The variety Bezostaya 1 produced the highest grain yield on average. Overall, significantly higher values of yield, and yield components were achieved in the nitrogen fertilization treatment compared to the unfertilized treatment. The yield difference in favor of the fertilized treatment ranged from 2% for the variety Crnozrna to 11% for the variety Bankut 1205.

Keywords: *winter wheat, old varieties, landraces, nitrogen, yield components, yield.*

Introduction

Old, traditional wheat varieties and local landraces are considered significant sources of natural variability in important agronomic and nutritional traits, some of them with good tolerance to abiotic stress factors (Miroslavljević et al., 2021) and good ability to remobilize nutrients to the grain (Mikić et al., 2023). Their diversity can have substantial advantages in unfavorable agroecological conditions and represent an alternative to modern varieties due to better adaptability to extensive production conditions. The value of local landraces and old wheat varieties is recognized primarily from a nutritional perspective. Modern varieties, compared to old varieties and landraces, often have lower protein and mineral element content. The content of carotenoids and micronutrients (Fe and Zn) is particularly low in the grains of modern varieties. Newton et al. (2011) and Aćin et al. (2023) highlighted that local landraces and old varieties are the richest sources of micronutrients, antioxidants, carotenoids, vitamins, and other specific bioactive components, thus playing an important role in the prevention of numerous diseases. Živančev et al. (2023) noted that landraces and old varieties of bread wheat, as well as einkorn, emmer, durum, and spelt wheat, have proven to be excellent sources of tocopherols, Fe, and Zn. Local landraces, old varieties, and varieties intended for organic farming have shown relatively high protein yields under extensive

production conditions and in less favorable agroecological conditions but exhibit low performance in favorable agroecological conditions and intensive production systems (Baresel et al., 2008).

Considering that old wheat varieties and landraces used to be cultivated in farming systems with very little inputs, they could meet the present needs for ecological, sustainable, integrated, and organic production, especially on marginal lands with poor soil fertility, especially in nitrogen, in less favorable agroecological conditions and under extensive production conditions. Especially in the context of climate change and the trend toward more sustainable agricultural production systems, there is a need for the availability and use of a broader collection of genetic resources. According to Newton et al. (2011), old varieties and landraces are a very valuable but underutilized resource in modern crop production. The overall improvement of agriculture, as well as selection and breeding, has led to a constant increase in wheat yields over the years. This has been accompanied by an increased need for higher amounts of mineral nutrients in high-yielding varieties to fully express their genetic potential in intensive farming (Jaćimović et al., 2023). However, the intensification of agriculture, characterized by high chemical application, as well as modern breeding activities, has not only reduced the biological diversity of cultivated species but also led to the near-complete neglect of old, traditional varieties and local landraces. Due to the ongoing trend of reintroduction old wheat varieties and landraces, and reducing the reliance of wheat production on nitrogen fertilizers, it is necessary to re-examine their agro-morphological and productive traits, as well as their response to basic agronomic practices in trials with no and with optimal nitrogen input. Therefore, the aim of this study was to compare performances and examine the effect of nitrogen fertilization omission, as well as its application in top-dressing, on the main yield components and grain yield of five old, traditional winter wheat landraces and varieties.

Material and Methods

The research was conducted as part of the FAO project GRAINEFIT led by the Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops in Novi Sad, Serbia. The project is focused on the conservation and sustainable use of neglected small grains genetic resources in the light of climate change. In addition, the aim of the project is to support small farms in achieving stable production and obtaining safe and high-quality grain products. The experiment was conducted during the 2022/2023 growing season, at the Agricultural school in Bačka Topola (45°47'34"N 19°35'52"E). Agro-ecological conditions are typical for the Pannonian region, with continental climate characterized by considerable temperature variations, and in recent decades, hot summers, more and more often mild winters, irregular rainfall distribution and frequent drought events. The weather data for the growing season 2022/2023 in Bačka Topola were shown on Figure 1.

Figure 1. The average temperatures (T) and precipitation (P) compared to their long-term averages (LT) per 10-day periods from October 2022 to June 2023 in Bačka Topola

The field trial area was on meadow soil, which had been cultivated without fertilizers application for years. The soil type on the experimental plot was chernozem, formed on a loess terrace. Agrochemical analyzed determined the soil quality, as well as the mineral nitrogen content by soil profile depth, to determine the fertilization needs for the selected wheat landraces and varieties. Soil analysis for basic agrochemical properties was performed in the fall of 2022 for determination of the necessary amounts of P and K. For determination of the mineral N content in the soil according to the N-min method, soil samples were taken using a manual probe in February 2023 at layers of 0-30 cm, 30-60 cm, and 60-90 cm. Based on the soil analysis results (Table 1), the soil was slightly alkaline. According to the CaCO_3 content, the soil belonged to the class of highly calcareous soils, while based on humus and total N content, it was moderately humic and moderately supplied with total N. The content of available P and K was very high, so there was no need for fertilization with these elements.

Table 1. Results of basic agrochemical properties of soil testing

Agrochemical properties of soil							
Depth (cm)	pH		CaCO_3 (%)	Humus (%)	Total N (%)	AL- P_2O_5 (mg/100 g of soil)	AL- K_2O
	in KCl	in H_2O					
0-30	7.60	8.11	12.89	3.04	0.180	84.84	57.20

The results of the determination of mineral nitrogen content and distribution in the soil according to the N-min method are presented in Table 2. The total amount of mineral N in the 0-90 cm layer was 52.14 kg ha^{-1} , which served as the basis for calculating the required amount of N for top-dressing. Based on the standard calculation, it was determined that 109 kg of active N ha^{-1} was needed for top-dressing wheat on the experimental plot. It was decided to split the calculated amount into two top-dressing applications in a ratio of 70% (basic dose of N): 30% (corrective top-dressing), i.e., $76 : 33 \text{ kg}$ of a.m. of N ha^{-1} . Given the very low mineral N content in the surface soil layer (12.90 kg ha^{-1} in the 0-30 cm layer), the top-dressing of wheat was carried out using a fast-release AN fertilizer (34% N).

Table 2. Results of mineral nitrogen (N-min) and soil moisture content analysis

Soil depth	N-min (kg N ha ⁻¹)	Soil moisture (%)
0-30 cm	12.90	25.6
30-60 cm	16.93	25.5
60-90 cm	22.31	23.9
Sum:	52.14	75.07

The experiment was conducted as a two-factorial, using a split-plot design with four replications and a randomized arrangement of treatments. The following factors and treatments were examined: Factor A - winter wheat varieties: S1 - Stara banatka, S2 - Bezostaya 1, S3 - Bankut 1205, S4 - Crnozrna, and S5 - Brkulja 4 (seeds obtained from the collection of the Institute of Field and Vegetable Crops); and Factor B: nitrogen fertilization in top-dressing, with two treatments: a) control treatment without N fertilization (N₀) and b) nitrogen fertilization in top-dressing based on soil N-min analysis (N₁₀₉).

After primary tillage (plowing to a depth of 25 cm) and pre-sowing soil preparation, sowing of the selected wheat varieties and landraces was performed on October 19, 2022. Sowing was done using a mechanical grain drill with a row spacing of 12.5 cm and a seeding rate of 500 viable seeds per m². Each variety was sown on an area of 30 m² (3 m width × 10 m length), with isolation paths of 1 m between varieties. Each main plot (i.e., variety) was divided lengthwise into two subplots: unfertilized (N₀) and fertilized with nitrogen in top-dressing based on N-min analysis (N₁₀₉). Each subplot was further divided into four replications, each measuring 1.5 m × 2.5 m. In the treatment planned to examine the effects of N fertilization, top-dressing of all varieties was performed twice: on February 18, 2023, at the tillering stage (base dose; 76 kg N ha⁻¹), and on March 9, 2023, before stem elongation phase (corrective top-dressing; 33 kg N ha⁻¹). The only maintenance measures applied were keeping the isolation paths and manual weed control. Harvesting of all experimental plots was carried out in late June 2023. The yields of dry grain (13% moisture) per plot were converted to t ha⁻¹. The effects of the analyzed factors and their interactions on yield components and grain yield of the examined varieties and landraces were processed using analysis of variance (ANOVA) for a two-factorial experiment conducted in a split-plot design with randomized treatment arrangements (GenStat for Windows 12th ed.). The statistical significance of treatment mean differences was determined by Fisher's Least Significant Difference (LSD) test at a significance level of 5%.

Results and Discussion

The analysis of variance for grain weight per spike, 1000-grain weight, and yield (Table 3) showed that both the analyzed varieties and nitrogen fertilization had a statistically highly significant effect on the total variability of all traits. The interaction effect of varieties and top-dressing was highly significant for grain weight per spike and grain yield, and significant for 1000-grain weight. Analysis of the contribution of individual sources of variation to the total sum of squares revealed that the varieties dominated with the largest share in the variability of all three traits, suggesting that there is a significant difference in the genetic potential for yield among the analyzed varieties, which can be attributed to their different origins and the presence of varietal specificity. The overall contribution of nitrogen fertilization and the interaction of varieties and fertilization was very low but still significant, indicating that N top-dressing also influenced the modification of the examined traits.

Table 3. Key indicators from the analysis of variance for grain weight per spike, 1000-grain weight, and grain yield in the experiment¹

Sources of variation	d.f.	Grain weight per spike			1000-grain weight			Grain yield		
		SS (%)	F	F-pr.	SS (%)	F	F-pr.	SS (%)	F	F-pr.
Replications	3	0.3	1.04	-	0.8	1.62	-	0.5	2.12	-
Varieties (A)	4	90.1	206.24	<0.001	90.6	145.61	<0.001	94.1	279.99	<0.001
Fertilization (B)	1	3.1	28.30	<0.001	2.5	16.38	<0.001	1.2	14.81	<0.001
A × B	4	3.5	8.03	<0.001	1.9	3.12	0.031	1.9	5.65	0.002
Error	27	2.9	-	-	4.2	-	-	2.3	-	-
Total	39	100	-	-	100	-	-	100	-	-

¹ **d.f.** - degrees of freedom; **SS (%)** - sum of squares (expressed as % of the total); **F** - F-test from the analysis of variance; **F-pr.** - probability (significance) of the F-test

Statistically significant differences in grain weight per spike were recorded among all analyzed varieties (Table 4). The highest value for this trait (1.67 g) was achieved by Crnozrna, while Stara banatka produced the lowest grain weight per spike. On average across varieties, significantly higher grain weight per spike (1.34 g) was obtained with N top-dressing treatment compared to the control treatment (1.23 g). This pattern of variation between N treatments was observed in Bezostaya, Bankut, and Brkulja, while no significant differences were observed between the N₀ and N₁₀₉ treatments in Crnozrna and Stara banatka. On average across both N treatments, the 1000-grain weight was highest in Bezostaya (37.6 g) and significantly higher compared to all other varieties. Brkulja and Crnozrna had lower but statistically similar 1000-grain weights, which were significantly higher compared to Stara banatka and Bankut. Across all analyzed varieties, significantly higher 1000-grain weight (31.1 g) was obtained with N top-dressing treatment compared to the control treatment (29.5 g). Higher 1000-grain weight with N top-dressing treatment was also observed for all individual varieties except for Crnozrna.

The highest grain yield was obtained from Bezostaya (3.66 t ha⁻¹), which was significantly higher compared to the other varieties (Table 4). Specifically, the grain yield of Bezostaya was 39% higher than Stara banatka, 32% higher than Bankut, 16% higher than Crnozrna, and 14% higher than Brkulja. On average across all five analyzed varieties, N-fertilization resulted in a significantly higher grain yield compared to the unfertilized treatment in the trial. The average yield difference in favor of N-fertilization was 0.11 t ha⁻¹ (or 4%). Only Stara banatka showed a higher grain yield in the control (N₀) treatment, while for all other varieties, the yield was higher in the N₁₀₉ treatment. The yield increased due to nitrogen application ranged from 2% for Crnozrna to 11% for Bankut.

 Table 4. Grain weight per spike (g), thousand grain weight (g), and grain yield of traditional winter wheat varieties (t ha⁻¹) as influenced by analyzed varieties and nitrogen fertilization

Grain weight per spike (g)			
Varieties (A)	Nitrogen fertilization (B)		Average (A)
	N ₀	N ₁₀₉	
Stara banatka	0.93 ^d	0.89 ^d	0.91 ^E
Bezostaya 1	1.43 ^b	1.60 ^a	1.52 ^B
Bankut 1205	0.94 ^d	1.11 ^c	1.03 ^D
Crnozrna	1.68 ^a	1.67 ^a	1.67 ^A
Brkulja 4	1.17 ^c	1.41 ^b	1.29 ^C
Average (B)	1.23^B	1.34^A	1.28

1000-grain weight (g)			
Varieties (A)	Nitrogen fertilization (B)		Average (A)
	N ₀	N ₁₀₉	
Stara banatka	24.8 ^{de}	25.3 ^{de}	25.0 ^C
Bezostaya 1	36.7 ^a	38.5 ^a	37.6 ^A
Bankut 1205	23.8 ^e	26.0 ^d	24.9 ^C
Crnozrna	32.0 ^c	31.8 ^c	31.9 ^B
Brkulja 4	30.3 ^c	34.1 ^b	32.2 ^B
Average (B)	29.5^B	31.1^A	30.3
Wheat grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)			
Varieties (A)	Nitrogen fertilization (B)		Average (A)
	N ₀	N ₁₀₉	
Stara banatka	2.29 ^f	2.15 ^g	2.22 ^D
Bezostaya 1	3.56 ^b	3.76 ^a	3.66 ^A
Bankut 1205	2.35 ^f	2.61 ^e	2.48 ^C
Crnozrna	3.06 ^d	3.12 ^{cd}	3.09 ^B
Brkulja 4	3.03 ^d	3.23 ^c	3.13 ^B
Average (B)	2.86^B	2.97^A	2.92

The treatment means labeled with different letters in the index indicate the presence of statistically significant differences ($p \leq 0.05$; LSD test)

Numerous studies have established that wheat yield depends on several key components: plant density, number of spikes per unit area, number and weight of grains per spike, and thousand grain weight. There are complex relationships among these indicators, as increasing one parameter often leads to a decrease in another (Hristov et al., 2008; Jaćimović et al., 2012). The significance of each of these components in yield formation depends on weather conditions during critical growth stages (especially water stress), as well as on applied agronomic practices, particularly the quantities and ratios of NPK nutrients (Hristov et al., 2011; Jaćimović et al., 2020). Several studies have shown that wheat growth and yield increase with fertilizer application up to a certain level, beyond which additional fertilization generally has no further positive impact, and at very high nutrient levels, yield reduction may occur (Aćin et al., 2016).

Conclusions

Our study revealed that all examined traits of traditional winter wheat landraces and varieties, had the greatest contribution to their variability, suggesting substantial genetic differences among the varieties, attributable to their different origins and specific varietal characteristics. The highest value for grain weight per spike was achieved by Crnozrna, while the lowest was by Stara banatka. On average, the grain weight per spike was significantly higher in the N-fertilized treatment compared to the control treatment. The highest 1000-grain weight was recorded in Bezostaya 1. Overall, for all varieties, a significantly higher thousand grain weight was obtained in the fertilized treatment compared to the unfertilized treatment. The highest grain yield was obtained in Bezostaya 1, and it was significantly higher compared to other varieties. Stara banatka produced the lowest grain yield. On average, across all varieties, N-fertilization resulted in a significantly higher yield compared to the unfertilized treatment.

Acknowledgement

The Benefit-Sharing Fund of the International Treaty on Plant Genetic Resources for Food and Agriculture project "Redesigning the exploitation of small grains genetic resources towards increased sustainability of grain-value chain and improved farmers' livelihoods in Serbia and Bulgaria-GRAINEFIT" (2020-2024), project number PR-166-Serbia.

References

- Aćin V., Jaćimović G., Denčić S., Jevtić R., Jocković B., Miroslavljević M. (2016). Effects of increasing doses of nitrogen and sowing densities on yield of winter wheat varieties in 2014/15. V Symposium of the Section for Organism Breeding, Kladovo, Book of Abstracts, 54-55.
- Aćin V., Miroslavljević M., Živančev D., Jocković B., Brbaklić Lj., Jaćimović G. (2023). Field management practices to produce nutritional and healthier main crops. Chapter 6. in Book: Developing Sustainable and Health-Promoting Cereals and Pseudocereals: Conventional and Molecular Breeding (Editors: Rakszegi, M., Papageorgiou, M., Rocha, J.M.). Publisher: Academic Press, Elsevier. 137- 173.
- Baresel J., Zimmermann G., Reents H. (2008). Effects of genotype and environment on N uptake and N partition in organically grown winter wheat (*T. aestivum* L.) in Germany. *Euphytica*, 163(3): 347-354.
- Hristov N., Mladenov N., Kondić-Špika A., Marjanović-Jeromela A., Jocković B., Jaćimović G. (2011). Effect of environmental and genetic factors on the correlation and stability of grain yield components in wheat. *Genetika*, 43(1): 141-152.
- Hristov N., Mladenov N., Špika A.K., Štatkić S., Kovačević N. (2008). Direct and indirect effects of certain traits on wheat grain yield. *Proceedings*, 45: 15-20.
- Jaćimović G., Aćin V., Miroslavljević M., Brbaklić Lj., Vujić S., Dunderski D., Šeremešić S. (2023). Effects of Combined Long-Term Straw Return and Nitrogen Fertilization on Wheat Productivity and Soil Properties in the Wheat-Maize-Soybean Rotation System in the Pannonian Plain. *Agronomy*, 13(6): 1529.
- Jaćimović G., Aćin V., Miroslavljević M., Jocković B., Brbaklić Lj., Živančev D., Ilin S. (2020). Response of some winter wheat cultivars to nitrogen topdressing and sowing density. „AgroSym 2020“, Book of Proceedings, 268-273.
- Jaćimović G., Malešević M., Aćin V., Hristov N., Marinković B., Crnobarac J., Latković D. (2012). Winter wheat yield and yield components depending on the level of nitrogen, phosphorus and potassium fertilization. *Annals of agronomy*, Faculty of Agriculture, Novi Sad, 36(1): 72-80.
- Mikić S., Takač V., Brbaklić L., Miroslavljević M., Trajković D., Buha N., Šumaruna, M. (2023). Estimation of yield potential of local wheat landraces with NDVI, flag leaf area and chlorophyll content. 12th International Symposium on Agricultural Sciences, Trebinje, Bosnia and Herzegovina. Book of Abstracts 81-82.
- Miroslavljević M., Mikić S., Župunski V., Špika A. K., Trkulja D., Ottosen C., Zhou R., Abdelhakim L. (2021). Effects of high temperature during anthesis and grain filling on physiological characteristics of winter wheat cultivars. *Journal of Agronomy and Crop Science*, 207(5): 823-832.
- Newton A.C., Akar T., Baresel J.P., Bebeli P.J., Bettencourt E., Bladenopoulos K.V., Czembor J.H., Fasoula D.A., Katsiotis A., Koutis K., Koutsika-Sotirio M., Kovacs G., Larsson H., Pinheiro M.A.A., Rubiales D., Russell J., Dos Santo T.M.M., Vaz Patto M.C. (2011). Cereal landraces for sustainable agriculture. *Sustainable agriculture*, Dordrecht: Springer. 147-186.

Živančev D., Buljovčić M., Ninkov J., Antić I., Mikić S., Jaćimović S., Jocković B. (2023).
Micronutrients composition of milling streams of traditional wheat cultivars. *Food and
Feed Research*, 50(1): 12-23.